

Synthesis and Reduction of Nitrones of Vanillin

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Manuscript received 17 April 1979, revised 6 July 1981, accepted 10 September 1981

Four new vanillin nitrones have been synthesized by condensing vanillin with various aryhydroxylamines. Reduction with sodium borohydride and deoxygenation with zinc dust and acetic acid were studied.

SYNTHESIS of nitrones of cinnamaldehyde was reported in an earlier communication¹. This communication deals with the synthesis and reduction reactions of nitrones of vanillin.

These nitrones have been synthesized by condensing vanillin with phenyl hydroxylamine, *p*-tolyl and *p*-chlorophenyl hydroxylamine and *p*-naphthyl hydroxylamine. The nitrones (Table 1) have been identified and confirmed by elemental analysis and spectral studies.

UV spectra of these nitrones indicate two maxima viz., 235 and 330 nm. IR spectra give bands at 1610 cm⁻¹ (>C=N-) and 1280-60 cm⁻¹ (N→O). In the nmr spectra, aromatic protons along with vinyl proton appears as a multiplet at 2.8τ, methoxyl protons as a singlet at 6.2τ and phenolic proton at 1.8τ.

Sodium borohydride reduction of these nitrones at room temperature yields the corresponding Schiff bases. However, if the temperature is raised, the Schiff bases are further reduced to the corresponding secondary amines². Warming with zinc dust and glacial acetic acid smoothly deoxygenates the nitrones to the corresponding Schiff bases (Scheme 1). The Schiff bases and secondary amines have been identified by m. p., m. m. p.², elemental analysis and comparison of uv, ir, nmr and mass spectra with those of authentic samples³.

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—VANILLIN NITRONES AND THEIR REDUCTION PRODUCTS

Sl. No.	R	Vanillin yield %	Nitrones m.p. °C	Deoxygenated products (Schiff bases)		m.p. °C	Secondary amines (NaBH ₄ at 50-60°)	
				Yield % with NaBH ₄ (Room temp.)	with Zn/ACOH		yield %	m.p. °C
1.	C ₆ H ₅	80	180	70	60	152	70	250
2.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	75	120	70	65	117	68	231
3.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	82	50	72	65	123	62	139
4.	C ₁₀ H ₇	60	85	65	60	157	60	185

All melting points are uncorrected.

All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis.

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Experimental

Synthesis of C-(p-hydroxy-m-methoxyphenyl)-N-phenyl nitrone: Phenylhydroxylamine (0.1 mole) was added to vanillin (0.1 mole) taken in chloroform (250 ml) with stirring and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 3-4 hr. Removal of the solvent gave crude product which was recrystallized from ethanol to yield bright yellow needles of the nitrone, m. p. 180° in 80% yield.

Reduction with sodium borohydride: Sodium borohydride (2.0 g) was added in small instalments to the nitrone (0.01 mole), prepared above, in methanol (50 ml) with stirring. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. It was then diluted with water and extracted with chloroform. Removal of the solvent gave the crude Schiff base which was recrystallized from ethanol to yield yellow crystals, m. p. 152° in 70% yield.

If the reaction mixture was warmed to 60° the Schiff base was further reduced to secondary amine, m. p. 250° in 70% yield.

Deoxygenation with zinc dust: Zinc dust (2.0 g) was added to the nitrone (0.01 mole) taken in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and the mixture was warmed on a water bath for 30 hr, then diluted with water and extracted with ether. Evaporation of the solvent yielded the crude Schiff base which was recrystallized from ethanol to give yellow crystals, m. p. 152° in 60% yield.

References

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3. M. RAI, "Dipolar Additions to Carbon-Nitrogen Double Bonds", Ph.D. Thesis, Punjabi University, Patiala, 1976.